

D2.3 Modularity and Dismantling guideline

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Executive summary

The first part of the deliverable 2.3 is a Statistical review of components around the cells/modules without any data on the cell composition / chemistry.

The second part is a design guideline for assembly-disassembly, ergonomic issues, Safety. This part also deals with design issues.

This document is intended to help the eco-design/conception of the MARBEL's battery pack and should be part of the guideline for safe and efficient process of dismantling and include modularity design criteria to prepare it for the second life.

This document is provided to evaluate some statistics from market batteries while the final design and composition of the battery arrives.

Table of contents

Deliverable Information sheet.....	2
Executive summary	2
Table of contents	3
List of figures	4
List of tables	4
1. Introduction.....	5
2. Results on statistical analysis of some market packs	5
2.1 Screw and steel rods	6
2.2 Specific metallic parts	7
2.3 Plastic components in the full packs	7
2.4 Metallic casing	7
2.5 Cells and modules	8
3. Dismantling process	9
3.1 Safety risks related to battery dismantling	9
3.2 Safety measurement aspects	11
3.3 Initial battery handling processes	14
4. Dismantling guideline	16
5. Manufacturability Guidelines	18
5.1 Design for Assembly/Disassembly (DFA)	18
5.1.1 Ergonomics:	18
5.1.2 Positioning and Handling	23
5.1.3 Tool access	24
5.1.4 Component workability and Rework-ability	25
5.1.5 Safety	27
5.2 Design for Manufacturing (DFM)	27
5.2.1 Material and Technologies Selection	27
5.3 Quality by Design (QbD)	28
5.3.1 Error proofing	28
5.3.2 Labelling and Traceability	29
5.4 Design to Cost (DTC)	30
5.4.1 Standardization	30
5.4.2 Module dimension	30
5.4.3 Discharging	30
5.5 Modularity	31
6. Conclusion.....	31

List of figures

Figure 1 Summary of 10 brands composition	6
Figure 2: Screws and metal rods.....	6
Figure 3: Some specific metal parts	7
Figure 4: Plastics items parts	7
Figure 5: View of some metallic casing	8
Figure 6: View of various modules	8
Figure 7: Various other modules leading to the dismantled cells.....	9
Figure 8: Safety risks involved in EV battery dismantling	10
Figure 9: Thermography of a EV battery	14
Figure 10: Service Disconnect	15
Figure 11: Voltage measurement	15
Figure 12: Battery traction system.....	16
Figure 13: Removal of battery casing	17
Figure 14: Measurements of the hands of men, women and children	19
Figure 15: Operator workstation	19
Figure 16: recommended working for the distance arms	19
Figure 17: Hand grip and position examples	20
Figure 18: Reaction force during screwing operation.....	20
Figure 19: Reaction arm device in plant.....	20
Figure 20: Weight limits for lifting in Italy.....	21
Figure 21: Weight limits according position.....	21
Figure 22: Weight limits according posture	22
Figure 23: Component dimension limits	22
Figure 24: Recommended ranges of optimal workbench heights for precision, light and heavy works.	22
Figure 25: Correct and wrong position for the operator	23
Figure 26: Field of vision	23
Figure 27: recommended head tilt and eye rotation angles	23
Figure 28: examples of positioning pins	24
Figure 29: Handling and positioning direction	24
Figure 30: Hard and Soft Poka-Yoke examples.....	28

List of tables

Table 1: composition and mass balance for 10 brands	5
Table 2: Safety measurements for working with EV batteries	13
Table 3: dismantling processes.....	18
Table 4: Risk associated with a battery.....	30

1. Introduction

The first part of the deliverable 2.3 is a Statistical review of components around the cells/modules without any data on the cell composition / chemistry.

The second part is a design guideline for assembly-disassembly, ergonomic issues, Safety. This part also deals with design issues.

This document is intended to help the eco-design/conception of the MARBEL's battery pack and should be part of the guideline for safe and efficient process of dismantling and include modularity design criteria to prepare it for the second life.

This document is provided to evaluate some statistics from market batteries while the final design and composition of the battery arrives. It reflects several years of experience where TES REC have dismantled and consolidates the data from 10 Brands (1 US, 2 Asia, 7 Europe).

The components were segregated as 6 families:

1. Screw and other small steel parts.
2. All plastics.
3. The external casing.
4. The electric and electronic items.
5. The cells or modules.
6. And the other specific elements (for example, some system has specific colling plates).

The second part of the report is related to Modularity and dismantling guideline. The task will set the basis and requirements for a modular battery easy to disassembly. Dismantling problems with the actual Battery Packs will be analysed. The requirements for the easy dismantling will be structured as simple protocol to be implemented during the design. In this task also the requirements for a versatile battery will be included, adaptable to any cells, chemistry, vehicle, etc.

2. Results on statistical analysis of some market packs

The details of the results obtained in the statistical analysis of a selection of actual battery packs present in the market are reported in next table:

Brand	Screws (steel)	plastics	casing	other specific elements	EEE	Cells/modules	Total
1	8.1%	4.9%	15.0%	7.0%	6.5%	58.5%	100.0%
2	0.5%	6.2%	15.0%	7.0%	3.4%	68.0%	100.1%
3	1.1%	6.6%	16.8%	7.0%	4.0%	65.0%	100.5%
4	1.9%	8.4%	10.0%	10.0%	5.0%	64.3%	99.7%
5	1.9%	8.7%	18.0%	9.9%	3.8%	58.0%	100.2%
6	1.7%	12.0%	9.9%	13.4%	3.3%	60.0%	100.4%
7	1.6%	8.8%	10.4%	11.5%	2.5%	68.0%	102.8%
8	1.3%	7.0%	12.0%	6.0%	3.7%	70.5%	100.5%
9	0.6%	8.3%	13.0%	7.9%	2.1%	69.8%	101.8%
10	1.4%	7.7%	13.0%	8.0%	2.6%	68.0%	100.6%

Table 1: composition and mass balance for 10 brands

The average composition is summarized in next graph:

Figure 1 Summary of 10 brands composition

2.1 Screw and steel rods

The typology of screws is reported for some brands.

Figure 2: Screws and metal rods

2.2 Specific metallic parts

In the following figures various specific items show the diversity of the material and products according to some market technologies. The materials are generally iron-manganese alloys or hard aluminum allied with Mn and Cu.

Figure 3: Some specific metal parts

2.3 Plastic components in the full packs

Several kinds of plastics parts are used as insulator and frame of the cells.

Figure 4: Plastics items parts

Generally, the composition is varying according to the brand but main materials are PP, ABS and PET with some linear sheet made by PEHD.

2.4 Metallic casing

The composition of the housing is carbon steel or hard aluminum generally with proprietary alloys.

Figure 5: View of some metallic casing

2.5 Cells and modules

The configurations of modules are numerous and strongly change from one brand to another.

Figure 6: View of various modules

The cells are in majority as pouch configuration. The rest is shared between cylindrical and prismatic.

Figure 7: Various other modules leading to the dismantled cells

3. Dismantling process

3.1 Safety risks related to battery dismantling.

The dismantling task starts with the mandatory safety evaluation and the implementation of safety actions in the area dedicated to the dismantling as well as individual protection of the workers. To avoid hazardous condition, the battery dismantling procedure needs to be carried out by qualified workers. This qualification, especially in handling HV batteries, are necessary to avoid dangerous situation related to battery disassembly operations. Several risks and hazards are associated with the battery handling operations during disassembly.

The hazard linked to the battery dismantling process are listed below:

1. **Electrical Hazards:** During part separation process, shorting of battery cells, short circuit in the battery system, and exposure of high voltage electrical energy are possible electric hazards that could happen. Figure 1 represents the possible types of hazards that could occur in EV battery.
2. **Thermal Hazards:** Thermal hazards are generally associated with the inner temperature of the battery such as elevated temperatures, fire, high temperature fluid release etc. Thermal runaway known as chaining and chemical reaction happens inside the battery cell at high inner temperature of battery is also thermal hazard that could cause fire incidents.
3. **Kinetic Hazards:** More risks associated with batteries comes under kinetic and chemical hazards. Because of high energy and power density, shock or blast waves can be generated by the batteries during the short circuit or being triggered by heavy load.
4. **Chemical hazards:** Some sort of toxic or flammable gases can get released if batteries are not handled properly. Solvents used in battery cells are flammable and electrolyte used in the batteries are toxic. Coming in direct contact with specific solutions or by inappropriate handling, they can release toxic and flammable gases.

Figure 8: Safety risks involved in EV battery dismantling

Apart from all these hazards, mechanical hazards during dismantling of batteries could also happen. These kinds of hazards are drop of tools, tool inclusion and inappropriate handling and operations of tools.

Causes of several hazards: These kinds of hazards are generally caused by various reasons. As EV batteries are richer in energy and power density, risks are mostly involved with the electrical aspect such as charging behavior of the batteries. Some of the causes for possible hazards in EV batteries have been mentioned below.

- Deep discharging: Being deep discharged, batteries can face mechanical stress which leads to poor conductivity of the battery and decreases their energy transfer capacity.
- Overcharging: Overcharging of battery occurred by the usage of wrong charger and false detection of battery voltage. This can cause an internal chemical reaction and results into the short circuit. Chances of short circuit are most likely to happen in anode as it ceases the lithium metal. While on the cathode, decomposition due to overcharging can generate heat.
- Short circuit: Short circuits can cause several electrical hazards. The chances of external short circuit are more when battery meets corrosion, electric shock, water, and several mechanical impact.
- Overheating: Overheating occurs when the temperature distribution in the battery is not uniform. Overheating of the battery can cause thermal runaway, fire explosions and capacity degradation.
- Mechanical damage: During the handling of the batteries, mechanical damage such as inappropriate use of tools, use of heavy load equipment can also cause structural damage in the battery. In the worst case, this can lead to fire and explosions.

3.2 Safety measurement aspects

The safety measures around the working place as well as protection equipment of operators are summarized in next table.

Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)		
Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) for working with EV batteries	Wearing insulating gloves complying with NF EN 60 903 and marked with a double triangle. Checking that gloves are leakproof before use	
	Wearing electrically insulating safety footwear or boots complying with standard NF EN 50 321	
	Wearing an arc protective mask	
	Wearing an insulating and shockproof safety helmet meeting NF EN 397	
	Wearing an arc flash jacket made of fire-retardant cotton or similar material	
Risks	Action	Scheme
Fire during disassembly	Ensuring early fire detection by monitoring certain points in the facility (e.g., the workplaces for the dismantling) using thermography and suction smoke detectors to detect fire gases and the release of very small amounts of electrolyte	
	Installing automatic countermeasures to developing fires using a close-meshed sprinkler network and a smoke extraction system	

	<p>Ensure the presence of a working fire extinguisher suitable for fires of electrical equipment (CO2, powder) nearby, both as a hand-held extinguishing unit at the workstations (9L) and as a mobile extinguishing unit (50L)</p>	
	<p>Keeping an extinguishing blanket made of fireproof textile fabric ready for battery fires at the individual workstations, which can be pulled over the battery in the case of a fire.</p>	
	<p>Existence of a suitable, fireproof emergency container that can spatially isolate the fire event.</p>	
Chemical hazard during disassembly	<p>Ensure the presence of safety showers and eyewash meeting the NF EN 15154 standard nearby (10 seconds walk maximum)</p>	
Electrical short circuit causing burns; electrification	<p>Visually ensure the absence of electrical risk near and at the battery (bare parts under tension, defective electrical insulation, ...)</p>	
	<p>To prevent the unintentional use of non-insulated tools (e.g., cover disassembly) on live parts (battery bridges), fully insulated bit holders should be used. Carry out the disassembly using isolated tools corresponding to the working voltage range and complying with the standard NF EN 60 900.</p>	
	<p>Installation of an insulating tapis meeting the standard NF C 18-420</p>	

	Protect the bare parts under tension of the various unit elements (cells or modules) disassembled on the battery with a suitable insulating protection (e.g., insulating tape)	
Electrification of a person not involved in disassembly	Tagging the dedicated area when a disassembly is in progress to prevent access to unqualified people	
Handling-related injuries	Use of a table at the appropriate height to avoid having to lower when disassembling. The working height is important for ergonomic work with the many screw connections to be loosened and heavy components to be lifted out. A scissor lift truck is an easy way to move batteries and lift them to a suitable working height.	
Electrolyte leaking from battery cells	Providing emergency kits, gas masks, extraction units	
Cell damage risk in current collector separation	effective use of specific binder (carboxymethyl cellulose and styrene-butadiene rubber) in anode and cathode materials	
Hazardous contamination between tools and battery parts	Specific set of tools to disassemble the parts	
Handling-related injuries	Use of a lifting device (forklift, pallet truck) to transport samples greater than 25 kg	
Propagation of thermal runaway potential from the battery to other used batteries	Perform disassembly in a dedicated and isolated location from battery storage areas	
	Ensure the absence of other batteries near the dedicated area when disassembling	

Table 2: Safety measurements for working with EV batteries

3.3 Initial battery handling processes

The initial battery handling process describes the procedures and actions relevant to the acceptance of EV batteries to guarantee the safety of the subsequent process as well as the successful execution of the downstream dismantling and discharging of the battery. In addition to the safety aspects to be complied with when unloading EV batteries, the focus here is particularly on those measures that are mandatory in preparation for the subsequent dismantling and discharging of the batteries.

The reception process can be divided into 5 steps, which are explained in more detail below:

1. Unloading
2. Visible Inspection
3. Thermography
4. Service Disconnect
5. Voltage Measurement

The **unloading** of the EV batteries from the transport vehicle, which, depending on the nature of the battery, must be delivered in ADR-compliant transport containers, is carried out with the help of a forklift truck. The forklift moves the battery to the area of the site designated for receiving. Once the battery has been unloaded, the transport container is opened, and the battery is subjected to various pre-inspection procedures which may only be carried out by trained HV electricians in compliance with applicable safety measures.

In a first step, the battery is **visually inspected**. For this, a trained high-voltage electrician examines whether the battery housing shows any damage that may have occurred during transport. In addition, it is checked whether liquids are leaking and whether smoke or heat is being generated. If one or more of the impairments are found on the battery during this inspection step, this battery must be sorted out and subjected to separate treatment, as the safety of the subsequent process may no longer be guaranteed.

If a battery shows none of these impairments, the next step is to perform a **thermography** to determine the internal temperature of the battery. Even without external influence, damage to the battery cell due to age-related damage to the separator and a subsequent short circuit cannot be completely ruled out. Due to the resulting rise in temperature the (usually highly flammable) electrolyte begins to vaporise and evaporate.

Figure 9: Thermography of a EV battery

As a result, the internal pressure in the cell rises until the electrolyte vapour is released either via a pressure relief valve or by the released by the bursting of the casing. Without countermeasures an explosive gas-air mixture is created. As this involves the risk of a thermal runaway and therefore fire if the battery temperature is too high, thermal validation of the battery before starting to dismantle and discharge is particularly important. If the internal temperature of the battery is within a non-critical range, the next steps of the pre-inspection can be carried out.

Figure 10 and Figure 11: Voltage measurement and Service Disconnect

The next step is to ensure that the HV system is voltage-free. This is an absolute prerequisite for safely carrying out further work on the battery. For this purpose, the so-called **service disconnect** is carried out, which ensures that the electric circuit of the battery and thus of the HV system is interrupted.

After the service disconnect is performed, the final step in preparation for battery dismantling is to take a **voltage measurement** to determine the remaining voltage of the still connected battery modules and compare it with the nominal / minimum / maximum voltage of the battery type.

When carrying out the five steps of the battery acceptance process, it must be ensured that all applicable safety standards are always observed. This is to ensure the accident-free running of the operation. For the first step of the process, unloading the battery from the transport vehicle, this implies that the Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) of the persons carrying out the operation must include safety shoes and a hard hat to protect themselves against the risk of falling objects. Work steps 2-5 of the pre-inspection of the battery may now only be carried out by HV electricians. The PPE required here must be adapted to the requirements of work under voltage. This includes at least insulating gloves according to DIN 60903, safety goggles, a safety helmet or electric arc protection screen with arc protection class 1 as well as safety shoes. For an overview of the required protective equipment for the different sources of danger when working on HV batteries, please refer to figure 9.

If, during the pre-inspection, a battery does not show any defects that may affect the safe performance of the downstream work, the battery is assigned to one of the workstations designated for further handling and dismantling is started. If a battery shows such defects or damage that could endanger the safety of further handling / processing, this battery must be assigned to a special workstation for damaged batteries. At this workplace, the defects of the battery are documented by a trained high-voltage electrician and a risk analysis of the battery in question is carried out. If the damage to the battery proves to be non-critical, it is stored separately from the undamaged batteries until the dismantling and discharging process begins.

4. Dismantling guideline

The dismantling process of Li-ion batteries is complex as it involves different kind of cell designs, variable quantity of cell used, different varieties of screws, bolts, components, etc. Some potential risks are involved with the high voltage battery cells. The construction of battery involves mainly cells, modules, battery case/pack, battery management system and power electronics. Different number of battery cells can be combined to form one module and different number of modules can be put together to form a battery pack/case.

In addition, a Battery Management System (BMS) has been attached to the battery pack with heating and cooling equipment. Moreover, battery packs are placed in an insulated casing to avoid hazardous conditions. The schematic of battery traction system is shown in figure 12.

Figure 12: Battery traction system

Several parts need to be disassembled in the pre-defined sequence. The main parts involved in this dismantling process are side brackets, battery case, BMS unit, BMS wires and plugs, module cover, HV bridges, cable ties, connectors, and battery modules. In general, the removal process sequence of above-mentioned parts can be done in the following way.

A Battery is generally covered with a casing on top and bottom sides. In order to remove these casings, the side brackets need to be removed first. After removing the side brackets, the screws must be disconnected from both top and bottom side casings (as shown in fig. 3). The casing can be removed by hands afterwards. Next, the high voltage fuse and battery strings needs to be separated from the battery case.

In the next step, the BMS unit can be dismantled by removing the battery connectors and cable ties. In the removal process of BMS, worker should take care of the state of charge (SoC) of the battery system. System voltage of the battery should be less than 60V to make the disassembly process safe. A higher active voltage of the battery can cause fire incidents and other injuries during the operation. Lastly, plug connections must be separated from BMS before removing it from the battery pack.

The module cover needs to be separated to get access to the battery modules. Retaining bracket must be separated from the module cover at the first place. In this process, different screw drives are generally used to untighten the bolts and screws of various sizes. Worker should take care of avoiding cell shorting while using screw drivers made from metal.

Figure 13: Removal of battery casing

Dismantling process of all active covers, cable guiding, and gas venting can be carried out during this time. Connectors between modules must be dismantled before removing battery modules from the case.

Other ends of BMS wires and connectors needs to be disconnected from the battery modules. For the same removal of battery modules, ring cables busbar and filter unit can be dismantled, and further recycling process can be carried out with it.

To summarize all these dismantling processes, the section of the battery, process name, brief process description and tools used are mentioned below in a table form.

Section	Process	Steps	Tools used
Side brackets	Getting access to cover screws	Remove the screw below the HV connector	Ring or open-end spanner
Battery case	Disconnection from power supply	Remove the HV fuse, separate the battery strings and HV bridges	Hand
BMS unit	Separation of BMS from battery case	Remove all the connectors from battery BMS unit. Remove HV fuse holder by loosening the screws and unscrewing the retaining bracket	Voltmeter
Module Cover	Module cover separation	Loosen the retaining bracket of module cover and then remove the "rear module cover"	Screw drivers
HV Bridges	Separation of HV bridges	Remove battery connections and HV bridges at the front side of the battery	Hand

Section	Process	Steps	Tools used
BMS plugs and wires	Removal of BMS wiring system from battery module	Disconnect all the cable ties after loosening the plugs and remove the BMS wiring	Side cutters
Battery modules	Removal of battery modules	Loose the retaining bolts of battery modules and start the separation of each battery module individually	Screw drivers
	Remover of each HV module cover	Disconnect the ring cable and lugs of HV connection	Cutters, hand
	Busbar and filter unit removal (if any)	Loosen the nuts and screws to disconnect busbar and filter from HV module	Screw drivers, Hand
	Busbar holder removal (if any)	Remove the holder of busbars and separate the battery module cover	Side cutters

Table 3: dismantling processes.

Current challenges regarding the dismantling of EV Batteries:

Looking at the current design of different types of EV batteries, several aspects currently increase the complexity of battery dismantling:

- One challenge is the different types of screws used, both between different battery types, but also for a single EV battery. These increase the duration of dismantling, as it is often necessary to switch between different screwdrivers. In addition, the screws are often not accessible from the same direction, which further increases the complexity and may require special tools.
- The use of glues presents another difficulty in the context of EV battery dismantling. These are sometimes more complicated to remove than screw or plug-in connections, which further increases the overall duration of the process.
- If a battery is cooled by means of coolant instead of air or water cooling, this is associated with additional safety risks and a costly and time-consuming extraction of the coolant. In these cases, it must be ensured that the use of the coolant is marked on the battery and that it is easily accessible for the dismantling process so that it can be extracted without difficulty.

The complexities and differences in the dismantling of different EV batteries created by these aspects currently make it necessary to make dismantling instructions battery type specific rather than generic. In this context, design changes to already known battery types pose a major problem. These result in the typification of a battery and thus also the dismantling instructions and the associated training for persons who are to work on this battery having to be prepared again, which results in a considerable additional expenditure of time and money.

The full view of dismantling guideline will include the following road map.

5. Manufacturability Guidelines

5.1 Design for Assembly/Disassembly (DFA)

5.1.1 Ergonomics:

The battery pack and the modules shall be able to be assembled and disassembled by an operator without any ergonomic issues in terms of:

5.1.1.1 Manual Operations

The battery pack components shall be designed in order to optimize the time needed for the assembly and disassembly procedures. Furthermore, wherever it is necessary to carry out maneuvers or manual operations, they shall be feasible and the components and the battery must guarantee sufficient space for the hands, as defined by International Ergonomics standards.

Figure 14: Measurements of the hands of men, women and children

The operator shall also have enough space for moving parts and tools to the desire locations.

Figure 15: Operator workstation

Figure 16: recommended working for the distance arms

5.1.1.2 Maximum force and tightening torque

During prototype and/or manual assembly and disassembly, the manual operations shall be easy and feasible for the operator and the use of special tool shall be minimized to decrease the time and increase the safety and the ease of operations for the operator. To avoid the use of pushing tools, hammers and

other dangerous and not allowed tools during the assembly and disassembly and allow manual operations the manual insertion forces shall be limited to the maximum allowed in the Standard ISO 11228.

Figure 17: Hand grip and position examples

All the operations that need a force higher than the max allowed threshold value shall be modified in the design phase where possible. If high efforts cannot be avoided, each incriminated operation shall be discussed with the assembly team to introduce countermeasure, dedicated equipment and process solution.

The fixations in the battery shall be designed in order to allow that all manual tightening torque for the fixations and fasteners are lower than the maximum torque allowed in the Standard ISO 11228.

Figure 18: Reaction force during screwing operation

Figure 19: Reaction arm device in plant

All the fixations with a tightening torque higher than this threshold value shall be discussed with the assembly team during the design phase to verify possible countermeasure as reaction arms and/or fixed screwing tools. The number of tools shall be minimized and simplified to avoid the presence of difficult

equipment to move. The tools shall be easily movable and opportunely sized to decrease the time needed for assembly and disassembly the battery.

5.1.1.3 Maximum components weight

The weight of the components and subassemblies that needs to be handled by an operator to allow modules and battery assembly and disassembly without additional tools shall be less than the maximum weight defined by Standard ISO 11228.

The value of the maximum weight shall also consider:

- the number of repetitions in a single working shift,
- the time the component needs to be carried,
- the distance covered by an operator carrying parts,
- the position upon which the component has to be placed,
- the operator posture etc.

Figure 20: Weight limits for lifting in Italy

Threshold values can be then more restrictive than those indicate above and shall be defined case by case. For example, according the ISO 11228 when the frequency of the operations increases, the weight of the load must be correspondingly reduced. The weight must be reduced also according the maximum total weight in one workday and if the distance from start to end is more than 10 meters.

Figure 21: Weight limits according position

Figure 22: Weight limits according to posture

The primary goal is to preserve health and safety of the operators and, in case of need, the design authority shall implement countermeasures in compatibility with the work environment.

5.1.1.4 Components Dimension

All the components and/or preassembled subgroups that must be installed in the battery shall have dimensions smaller than the maximum dimension that an operator can carry according to the Standard ISO 11228.

This entails not only a proper component sizing, but the identification of methods to give the operator the possibility to handle the component without any difficulties (distance of handling points, position of handling points, ...). The components shall be designed for an optimal grip to avoid the possibility to drop cumbersome parts and prevent any damage. Therefore, each part exceeding certain dimensions shall already be designed considering how the parts itself shall be handled in the assembly environment.

Figure 23: Component dimension limits

5.1.1.5 Posture, position and visibility

The operator shall have access to the desired location and all locations shall be reachable without any difficult body postures or posture that may endanger the operator safety

Figure 24: Recommended ranges of optimal workbench heights for precision, light and heavy works.

Figure 25: Correct and wrong position for the operator

Blind operations are not allowed. All the operations during assembly and dismantling shall be within the viewing zone. The area where a component will be installed shall be visible and easy to reach by hands before and during assembly operations. If not possible, countermeasures, as physical features and/or reference system, shall be introduced.

Figure 26: Field of vision

Figure 27: recommended head tilt and eye rotation angles.

5.1.2 Positioning and Handling

The operations needed for positioning, handling and fixing a component are of a crucial importance in the DfA assessment. The design of battery pack and modules shall focus not only on the 3D final configuration but also on component interaction during installation and dismantling. Components handling, positioning and fixation are therefore topics that shall be addressed from the early design phase throughout the full battery development. A change due to assembly issues in a late stage of development may have disruptive impacts both on time and cost without considering that the desired results and improvements might not be even reached.

5.1.2.1 Positioning

Physical positioning features and references are the preferred solution to help the operators for the component physical alignment during assembly procedures.

Figure 28: examples of positioning pins

These features shall guide the operator for the correct installation of the larger and most complex components in both battery pack and sub-assemblies. These identification features might be on the neighboring components or in the installation area. The component to component clearances during installation and dismantling shall guarantee no risk of touching and damaging the part that is being handled as well as the neighboring components. The minimum distance along the loading path of each component shall consider the clearance in the worst tolerance condition.

5.1.2.2 Handling Direction

The preferred loading path for the internal components of the battery during the installation and dismantling shall be in vertical direction.

Figure 29: Handling and positioning direction

If possible, the assembly of components shall avoid loading path with more than one direction for the installation in the battery. An installation done in a single step and in a single direction decreases the time needed and reduce the risk of touching and damaging other components.

5.1.2.3 Fixation direction

The preferred fasteners direction for internal components shall be in the vertical direction. Deviations due to guarantee primary function shall be discussed and evaluated with the assembly team during the design phase.

5.1.3 Tool access

All the fixation points of the components shall be designed according these two characteristics:

- shall guarantee enough clearance for the tools to avoid clash and damages to the neighboring components.
- easily accessible for the tools

5.1.3.1 Tools Clearance

Components shall be designed in order to give enough space for the fixing tools. Component to component clearance in the battery shall be such to guarantee to the operator the tool accessibility for all the fixations.

Remark: Recommended tool clearance is 5 mm. This distance does not cover clearance and creepage

distances. The clearance shall consider the tools used during the assembly and disassembly procedure and, then, all the needed features and tool characteristics (e.g. HV additional covers, thickness of the tools, features or specific tools used in specific operations and so on)

5.1.3.2 Tools accessibility

To ease the dismantling all the fixation points of every removable component shall be accessible by the tools without additional operations. The possibility to have tools accessibility gives the opportunity to reduce a lot the rework operations and the time needed to replace a component, also decreasing the possibility to damage other components during the operations. The removable components shall be defined at the first stage of the project and the design of the battery shall guarantee the dismantling of these components without the necessity to remove other components. This requirement is mandatory for all the serviceable components and for the components with a high probability to be replaced.

5.1.4 Component workability and Rework-ability

The battery development shall be focused on the workability and rework-ability of the components to allow their reuse, second life and recyclability. The components in the battery and modules shall allow the dismantling and maintenance of the battery without damaging and compromising functionality of the components. After a clear definition of all the components that could be reusable and/or recyclable the design of the overall battery and of the components shall apply all the features and measures able to maximize the rework-ability. Process and product countermeasures shall be applied to reach the target.

5.1.4.1 Component reuse

Each component of the battery shall be selected/designed in such way that once disassembled no damage appears on the component itself and/or on the system. For instance, the battery cells and modules shall be removable without mechanically or electrically compromising their primary functions, so that they may be salvaged, in their entirety to be immediately used without additional processes. The development of reversible joining technologies into the HVBS is important to reach this target.

5.1.4.2 Electronic units

To allow a second use of components the electronic units shall not be integrated in the components and shall be easily removed and substituted. The average life of an electronic device is usually shorter than the component where it is applied and after the component dismantling the electronic is probably obsolete. The interfaces of the electronic units (geometrical, electrical, and physical) shall be standard, to be compatible with other devices and other applications.

5.1.4.3 Cooling system

The cooling system shall be designed to be easily emptied before the disassembly and maintenance operations. Its removal should be independent from that of other components. The reduction of the risk to have liquid coolant during battery disassembly shall improve the safety of the operators that will handle the HVBS after its operative life.

5.1.4.4 Sub-assembly

The design of the battery and of the components shall be focused to decrease the time and the number of the needed operations for assembly and disassembly. This goal can be reached with a reduction of the design complexity and of the number of the parts to be assembled. This can be further enhanced by intruding operations that can be performed in parallel. Sub-groups shall be introduced in the design phase to have operations in parallel to the main assembly flow. All the subgroups shall be compatible with the maximum weight and dimension and all the ergonomic requirements.

5.1.4.5 Covers/components connection

For an easy removal and dismantling no component shall be installed on the hidden/internal side of covers. Component installation on the exterior/visible side is allowed. It is recommended to have covers and service door as stand-alone parts.

5.1.5 Safety

Assembly and disassembly risks shall be assessed in the early stage of the battery development and monitored throughout the project. Risks shall be evaluated case by case to define countermeasures to improve safety during assembly, rework and dismantling.

The safety shall be ensured by a correct design aimed to reduce all the possible risks. When design solutions are not possible/appropriate, the safety of the assembly operations will be handled by the assembly process. Safety of the dismantling procedure of abuse and aged battery packs needs a dedicated assessment that cannot be covered by the battery design itself.

The risks associated with a battery pack can have different nature.

	Potential hazards when using HV Li-Ion energy storage systems
	Electrical hazard Li-Ion HVBS is high voltage device. Li-Ion cells inside the HV Battery remains energized even when HV Battery is disconnected. Risk of electrical shock. Risk of sparking or arcing due to short circuit.
	Chemical hazard Li-Ion HVBS includes chemicals that may be harmful to humans in sufficient concentrations. Under certain severe failure conditions these chemicals may be leaked or emitted out of the HVBS. Risk of intoxication. Refer to Li-Ion cells material safety datasheet for further information regarding the chemical risks.
	Fire or Explosion hazard Li-Ion HVBS includes chemicals that may be flammable and/or explosive. Under certain severe failure conditions these chemicals may be leaked or emitted out of the HVBS. Risk of fire or explosion.
	Thermal hazard Parts of Li-Ion HVBS get hot during the operation or in fault conditions. Risk of burns and scalds.
	Mechanical hazard Li-Ion HVBS is heavy. Risk of crush or impact due to the heavy weight

Table 4. Risks Associated with a Battery.

5.2 Design for Manufacturing (DFM)

5.2.1 Material and Technologies Selection

In the next years the number of batteries will increase, and the reuse and recycling will be a crucial aspect to consider for a sustainable development of this technology in terms of material sources, costs and environmental impact. Technologies and material selection during the concept and development phase of components and battery packs will become more and more important and will be increasingly focused on disassembly, reuse, second life and recycling.

5.2.1.1 Material selection

The number of different materials shall be minimized. Recycled, recyclable and reusable materials shall take priority over other materials. When selecting a material for a component, the substances used in the manufacturing process shall be also taken into account: environmental impact of joining, gluing, gap filling and cleaning material and substances shall be considered.

5.2.1.2 Technologies selection

A similar assessment shall be done on the manufacturing process of the battery pack on the assembly line and later on, on the dismantling, reuse and recycling processes. The use of liquid pastes, liquid seals and liquid gap fillers shall be reduced in favor of removable pads and gaskets. Not reversible joining methods shall be evaluated case by case in search for possible alternatives. Welding between battery components in the main assembly flow are not allowed.

5.3 Quality by Design (QbD)

5.3.1 Error proofing

The operator shall be able to assess the correct installation of each component in the battery pack. Design features shall be introduced to help the operator to evaluate correct position and orientation of the components. The operator shall also receive a clear feedback that the operation is properly done in order to opportunely track in the assembly checklist the correct installation or any deviation.

5.3.1.1 Poka Yoke

Design features shall be introduced to ease operations during installation and dismantling of the battery. Poka-yoke features shall be introduced where there is the chance to connect or install a component in a wrong way or the wrong component in a similar place. Error proofing features could be physical barriers (hard poka yoke) or mere indication (soft poka yoke).

Figure 30: Hard and Soft Poka-Yoke examples

Hard poka yoke features are recommended for all the operation where an error can compromise performances, functionality and safety of the system.

5.3.1.2 Feedback

it is important to give the operator the possibility to clearly and easily detect if an operation is properly done. The feedback can be a sound, a secondary lock a change in position and/or a change in shape.

5.3.1.3 Automatized process

Design solutions that allow automatized assembly and dismantling shall be introduced wherever possible. Automatized processes allow to reduce the time needed for assembly and disassembly and could help during the recycling processes. Design for disassembly by automated or semi-automated processes is already in use in electronic industry to recover valuable electronic components for reuse.

5.3.1.4 Fastener operation

The tightening procedure of fasteners of the same type, has as prime target the functional performance of the single joint. Nevertheless, the same tightening torque shall be applied to fasteners of the same type wherever possible.

5.3.1.5 Unlosable screws

Safety critical connections shall make use of unlosable screws (screws retained by features of the component itself). No use of washer is recommended, but in case of need, the washer shall be unlosable. Loosening of metallic components in a battery pack can create immediate risks for the operator and in the long-term endanger battery operations.

5.3.2 Labelling and Traceability

In the scenario of a large battery recycling or reuse, the lifetime of a single component is not strictly limited to the usage on the first battery pack, but it will be extended to other application. In order to provide enough information to the people that will handle the parts, opportune tracking methods need to be established.

5.3.2.1 Traceability

All the components shall have a proper traceability throughout their own specific lifetime. For a proper traceability every subgroup or components that could be replaced shall have marking or a specific label (e.g. Barcode, QR Code).

5.3.2.2 Labelling

The info needed on the labelling for each component/subgroup shall be defined according international standards and regulations. Labels shall contain all the safety recommendations and warnings. Labels shall be designed to survive across the whole component lifetime. Component marking shall comply with IMDS Standards.

5.3.2.3 Lifetime

The lifetime shall be defined component by component to consider reuse and the second life application. Lifetime of a component may exceed the one of the first battery pack.

5.4 Design to Cost (DTC)

5.4.1 Standardization

To make reuse and recycling sound more attractive they shall be economically feasible. Being this a subject of vast complexity, the development process of a battery pack may apply some guideline:

5.4.1.1 Component standardization

Decrease assembly and disassembly costs and time and ease the reuse of the components for second life application

5.4.1.2 Fasteners homogenization

The development process shall be intended to reduce the number of fasteners type where a single type is identified by a variation of the one of the following geometrical characteristics: diameter, length, material, head shape, standard. The use of fasteners from a common standard largely available in the market is preferred

5.4.2 Module dimension

The module shall be designed following the standard dimension of modules defined by international standards (for example VDA Standards dimension or OEM best practices) in order to allow modularity and different applications. Remark: deviation due to cell dimension are accepted.

5.4.3 Discharging

Before the EV battery modules are deep discharged after the dismantling process, testing can be carried out to determine whether the battery cells are suitable for reuse in a second-life application, such as an energy storage solution. If this suitability is determined during battery testing, battery modules that are to be recycled must not be deep discharged, as discharging to a voltage range of 0V – 1V leads to the battery cell being irreversibly damaged. If, on the other hand, the voltage of individual cells of a battery module differs too much from other cells of the module during testing, the module is unsuitable for a second-life application and must be recycled.

For safety reasons, battery modules intended for recycling must be discharged before recycling or further disassembly of the modules. As the batteries have too much residual voltage for safe shredding even at a State of Charge (SOC) of 0 %, the batteries must be deep discharged. This reduces the risk of short circuits and the occurrence of fires when shredding the modules and/or cells. The energy extracted in the process should be recovered and reused in the so-called "energy harvesting" and used in the following process instead of being converted into heat. This offers the possibility to make the recycling process of EV batteries more energy efficient and consequently reduce the CO2 footprint of lithium-ion batteries.

5.5 Modularity

Modularity of battery packs for electric vehicles is crucial to have a good performance during dismantling in end-of-life and second life of the batteries.

The modularity must be included during the conception of the pack. This modularity is more focused on conception of modules and assembly making scalable packs.

In this work the modularity was already included in the several steps of the proposed protocol and guideline of dismantling EV packs.

The first sphere of modularity should be achieved at the conception by definition of versatile cells/modules able to be used for several field of application.

The second sphere will be focused on the conception of batteries in order to allow dismantling allowing modularity of the components in such way to favorize the second life in other segment than e-mobility (stationary , ex front to solar station etc..).

6. Conclusion

The average composition in term of cells/modules is almost equilibrated for several brands.

The impact of casing contribution is mainly linked to the materials used (steel or hard aluminum).

In some technologies, the percentage of screw is related to welding contribution.

The plastic fraction is in short range (between 5 and 8%) except for one particular design of one brand.

This is also the case for electric and electronic parts which are between 3 and 6%.

Safety of working place as well as protection will be implemented before starting any handling of batteries.

Preliminary guideline for dismantling is proposed including design guideline for assembly-disassembly, ergonomic issues, safety, design issues. It will be improved and completed when having the design of the full battery pack of the project.